

A SYSTEMIC MODEL TO SIMULATE THE FORMATION AND EMPLOYMENT IN “LA COMA”

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Abstract

“La Coma” is an outlying neighbourhood of the town of Valencia, its special and cultural frontiers that separate him from the urban centre, require new forms of social intervention. The integral plan of the local development in “La Coma” is the result of the work of the commissions created and constituted by the neighbours, university technicians and professionals that act in “La Coma” and the contributions carried out by the different departments of the autonomous and municipal administrations.

The integral plan is a work instrument, with clear objectives, that treats the problem of the “La Coma” in a global way fixing performance aims and measures of five areas: Formation and employment, life quality (infrastructure), health, education, coexistence and culture.

The integral plan can be suitably studied with the help of mathematical models. However, with the lack of the historical data we have limited our study to the area of the formation and employment with the purpose of answering the following questions:

How can we reduce the rate of the unemployment and increase the number of enterprises in “La Coma”?

What is the optimal strategy to follow in this study?

Resumen

El Barrio la Coma es un barrio periférico de Valencia capital, sus fronteras especiales y culturales que le separan del centro Urbano, requieren nuevas formas de intervención social. El plan integral del desarrollo local (Barrio la Coma) es el resultado del trabajo de las comisiones del Barrio creadas y constituidas por sus vecinos, las sugerencias hechas por técnicos universitarios y profesionales que actúan en el Barrio y las aportaciones realizadas por los distintos departamentos de las administraciones autonómica y municipal.

El plan integral es un instrumento de trabajo, con objetivos claros y con la fuerza del consenso, trata la problemática del Barrio de forma global fijando objetivos y medidas de actuación de cinco áreas: Formación y empleo, calidad de vida (viviendas u infraestructuras), salud, educación, convivencia y cultura

El plan integral puede ser convenientemente estudiado con ayuda de modelos matemáticos. Pero con la falta de los datos históricos hemos limitado nuestro estudio a la área de la formación y empleo con el fin de contestar las siguientes preguntas:

¿Cómo podemos reducir la tasa del desempleo en los habitantes del barrio la Coma?

¿Cómo podemos aumentar el número de empresas en el barrio?

¿Qué política tiene que seguir?

Deterministic Model

Work plan

- To find the factors or relevant variables.
- To find the influence relationships between the factors or variables previously identified.
- To find the equations or functional relationships that allow to determine the behaviour of each variable.
- To search for the necessary historical data for the calculation of the numeric constants that appear in the global behaviour model of the system.
- Validation of the model.

- Simulation of the control strategies.
- Selection of the optimal strategies (which lead to a maximum employment in each scenario).

Identification of the elements and codification

In this work we have followed the method Brainstorming to identify the elements.

The codification consists on giving a name to each element taken into account.

An element will have more than one dimension when we should distinguish its measure in different groups; for example, in the number of

workers it is interesting to separate the number of those that work self-employed (SE) of those that make it for other people count (OE).

The following list is the definitive one, not only obtained after the brainstorming, but also after the modifications introduced in the successive steps of the methodology:

ITML Transparency index of the work market
 NTRA(2) Increase of the (SE) (1)
 Increase of the (OE) (2)
 NUTR(2) Number of the (SE) (1)
 Number of the (OE) (2)
 NUTI(2) Initial number of the (SE) (1)
 Initial number of the (OE) (2)
 NTRD(2) Decrease of the (SE) (1)
 Decrease of the (OE) (2)
 DMCL Mean duration of contracts (months)
 NTDS (2) Discharged workers with
 professional formation (FP) (1)
 Discharges of the (OE) without
 FP (2)
 NMTE (2) Mean number of the (SE) by
 enterprise. (1)
 Mean number of the (OE) by
 enterprise. (2)
 NTTP Total Number of unemployed.
 NTPR (2) Number of unemployed with FP (1)
 Number of unemployed without
 FP (2)
 NTPI (2) Initial number of unemployed.
 NTPA (2) Increase of unemployed with FP (1)
 Increase of unemployed without FP
 (2)
 NINL (2) Immigrants workers number with
 FP (1)
 Immigrants workers number without
 FP (2)
 IPAC (2) Active population's increase with
 FP (1)
 Active population's increase without
 FP (2)
 NVAC(4) Number of vacancies in "La
 Coma" for people with FP (1)
 Number of vacancies in "La Coma"
 for people without FP (2)
 Number of vacancies the
 environment of "La Coma" for
 people with FP (3)
 Number of vacancies in
 the environment of "La Coma"
 for people without FP (4)
 NVAI (4) Initial number of vacancies
 NVAD (4) Decrease of vacancies

NVAA (4) Increase of vacancies
 DFIA Money to finance the self-employment
 CNCE Mean Capital necessary to create
 an enterprise
 TNCE Normal rate of the enterprises birth (%)
 SEAL Increase of enterprises
 NEMP Number of enterprises
 NEMI Initial number of enterprises
 NEMD Decrease of the number of enterprises
 TDEC Rate of enterprises decrease
 by competition (%)
 TNDE Normal rate of enterprises decrease (%)
 NPFP Posts number of FP
 NPFI Initial number of Posts of FP
 NPFA Increase of posts of FP
 NPFD Decrease of posts of FP
 NFOR Numbers of new formed with FP
 PTAT Percentage of temporary workers
 among the (OE) (%)
 PFPA Percentage of workers with FP among
 the (OE)
 PTBA(2) Percentage of workers that work
 in "La Coma" with FP (1)
 Percentage of workers that work
 in "La Coma" without FP (2)
 TRCP Retard time of posts creation of FP
 NCAP Number of apparent necessary FP posts
 NCAI Initial Number of apparent necessary
 FP posts
 NCRE Real number of necessary FP posts
 ECPL Excess of FP posts
 ECAP Excess of apparent posts
 ECAI Initial number of apparent excess
 of posts
 TREP Retard time of FP posts excess.
 NVAE (2) Forecast of the number of
 vacancies of the environment
 with FP (1)
 Forecast of the number of
 Vacancies of the environment
 without FP (2)
 NTRR (2) Number of discharged workers
 with FP (1)
 Number of discharged workers
 without FP (2)
 NTRI (2) Initial number of discharged workers
 OBJE Objective to maximize
 OBJM Mean annual objective to maximize
 DFII Initial value of the money to finance
 the
 self-employment
 DFAM Monthly money received to finance
 the
 self-employment

Forrester Diagram

(See **FIGURE.1**)

Formulation of the equations

To program the model, it is not only necessary to know how the variables are related among themselves, but also it is necessary to know with which language they should be communicated to the computer. Next, we present the equations of the model

Equation 1

```
NTRA if i1=1 then
  ntra(1)=nema*nmte(1)
else
  na=nvai(1)+nvai(3);nb=nvai(2)+nvai(4)
  if ntpi(1)<=na then
    ntra(2)=ntpi(1)*itml/100
  else
    ntra(2)=na*itml/100
  if ntpi(2)<=nb then
    ntra(2) = ntra(2)+ntpi(2)*itml/100
  else
    ntra(2)=ntra(2)+nb*itml/100
  endif
endif
endif
```

Equation 2

```
NTRD ntrd(i1)=nemd*nmte(i1)
  if i1=2 then ntrd(2)=ntrd(2)+ntds(1)+ntds(2)
```

Equation 3

```
NTRR if i1=1 then
  ntrr(1)=ntri(1)+(nuti(2)*ptat*pfpa/10000-
  ntri(1))/dmcl
  if i1=2 then
  ntrr(2)=ntri(2)+(nuti(2)*ptat*(100-pfpa)/10000-
  ntri(2))/dmcl
```

Equation 4

```
NTDS if i1=1 then
  ntds(1)=(nuti(2)*ptat*pfpa/10000 - ntri(1))
  /dmcl
  if i1=2 then ntds(2)=(nuti(2)*ptat*(100-
  pfpa)/10000-ntri(2))/dmcl
```

Equation 5

```
NUTR nutr(i1)=nuti(i1)+ntra(i1)-ntrdi1)
```

Equation 6

```
NTPA if i1=1 then
  ntpa(1)=ntrd(1)+ntrd(2)*pfpa/100
  if i1=2 then ntpa(2)=ntrd(2)*(100-pfpa)/100
  ntpa(i1)=ntpa(i1)+ninl(i1)+ipac(i1)
```

Equation 7

```
NTPR ntpri(i1)=ntpi(i1)+ntpa(i1)
  if i1=1 then ntpri(1)=ntpr(1)-ntra(1)-
  ntra(2)*pfpa/100+nfor
```

```
  if ntpri(1)<0 then ntpri(1)=0
  if i1=2 then ntpri(2)=ntpr(2)-ntra(2)*(100-
  pfpa)/100+nfor
  if ntpri(2)<0 then ntpri(2)=0
```

Equation 8

```
NVAD if i1=1 then
  nvad(1)=ntra(1)*ptba(1)/100 +
  ntra(2)*pfpa*ptba(1)/10000
  if i1=2 then nvad(2)=ntra(2)*(100-
  pfpa)*ptba(2)/10000
  if i1=3 then nvad(3)=ntra(1)*(100-ptba(1))
  /100 + ntra(2)*pfpa*(100-ptba(1)) /10000
  if i1=4 then nvad(4)=ntra(2)*(100-
  pfpa)*(100-ptba(2)) /10000
```

Equation 9

```
NVAA if i1=1 then nvaa(1) = nema*nmte(1) +
  nema*nmte(2)*pfpa/100 + ntds(1)*ptba(1)/100
  if i1=2 then nvaa(2)=nema*nmte(2)*(100-
  pfpa)/100 + ntds(2)*ptba(2)/100
  if i1=3 then nvaa(3)=nvae(1)
  if i1=4 then nvaa(4)=nvae(2)
```

Equation 10

```
NVAC nvac(i1)=nvai(i1)+nvaa(i1)-nvad(i1):if
  nvac(i1)<0 then nvac(i1)=0
```

Equation 11

```
SEAL a=nemi*tnce;b=dfii/cnce:
  nema=int(a)+int(b)
```

Equation 12

```
NEMD nemd=nemi*(tnde+tdec)
```

Equation 13

```
NEMP nemp=nemi+nema-nemd
```

Equation 14

```
NCRE na=nvai(1)+nvai(3);nb=nvai(2)+nvai(4)
  if(na>nb and ntpi(2)>na)then ncre=na
  if(na>nb and ntpi <na)then ncre=ntpi(2)
  if (na <nb) then ncre=0
```

Equation 15

```
NCAP ncap=ncai+(ncre-ncai)/trcp
```

Equation 16

```
NPFA npfa=(ncre-ncai)/trcp: if npfa <0 then
  npfa=0
```

Equation 17

```
ECAP ecap=ecai+(ecpl-ecai)/trep
```

Equation 18

```
NPFD npfd=(ecpl-ecai)/trep:if npfd <0 then
  npfd=0
```

Equation 19

```
NPFP npfp=npfi+npfa-npfd
```

Equation 20

```
NTTP nttp=ntpi(1)+ntpi(2)
```

Equation 21

```

ECPL nc=nvai(1)+nvai(3)
  if ntpi(2)<nttp*0.1 then
    ecpl=npfi
  elseif nc <ntpi(1)*0.2 then ecpl=npfi
  elseif ntpi(1)>nttp*0.9 then ecpl=npfi
  else ecpl=0
  endif

```

Equation 22

```

NFOR if abs((t mod 12)-6)<0.001 then
nfor=npfi/2 else nfor=0

```

Equation 23

```

OBJE obje=(nmte(1)+nmte(2)) *nemp/nttp

```

Equation 24

```

DFIA if dfii>=cnce then dfia=dfii mod cnce else
dfia=dfii
dfia=dfia+dfam

```

Equation 25

```

OBJM if (t-1) mod 12 <.001 then
  XA=0:XA=XA+obje:objm=0
else
  if t mod 12 <.001 then
    objm=(XA+obje)/12
  else
    XA=XA+obje
  endif
endif

```

Programming for the computer

The previous equations are written in an easily way adaptive to the most of the programming languages. In this work we have used the software SIGEM built by Antonio Caselles Moncho (Department of Applied Mathematics, University of Valencia).

Verification of the Model

- Strategy 1: to maximise the ITML and the DFAM.
- Strategy 2: to maximise only the ITML.
- Strategy 3: to maximise only the DFAM.
- Strategy 4: to minimise the ITML and the DFAM.

	Strategy 1	Strategy 2	Strategy3	Strategy 4
Tender Scenario	E(T,1)	E(T,2)	E(T,3)	E(T,4)
Pessimist scenario	E(P,1)	E(P,2)	E(P,3)	E(P,4)
Optimist scenario	E(O,1)	E(O,2)	E(O,3)	E(O,4)

Initial values of the level variables

NUTI(1) Initial number of the (SE)
 NUTI(2) Initial number of the (OE)
 NTPI(1) Initial number of unemployed with (FP)
 NTPI(2) Initial number of unemployed without FP
 NVAI(1) Initial number of local vacancies with FP
 NVAI(2) Initial number of local vacancies without FP

The verification of the model consists in detecting or rather correcting syntax and calculation errors that exist in the model.

Validation of the model

With the scarcity of the results of the reality, we have investigated carefully the equations of the model and their relationships. Then we have carried out many experiments fixing our efforts in the sense of the results.

Model use

This model has been built, fundamentally to control the formation and employment in “La Coma”, for that reason, it is necessary to propose control strategies and to have a certain objective in order to choose the best one.

Control strategies and scenarios in the model

Once designed, developed, validated the dynamic model, this can be used to simulate the behaviour of the system and its time evolution, in very diverse external circumstances and with a great variety of control strategies. Therefore, different evolutions of the variables considered as input variables of the model and different performances in the variable calls of control can be used to generate a limitless number of situations in which we could simulate the behaviour of the system, and to analyse its future evolution.

It is assumed equally that with the uncontrollable variables such scenarios can be built as the tender, the pessimist and the optimist. Each strategy can be experimented in each one of the outlined scenarios, producing a value to optimise for the variable (the objective variable).

NVAI(3) Initial number of vacancies of the environment with FP
 NVAI(4) Initial number of vacancies of the environment without FP
 NEMI Initial number of enterprises in “La Coma”
 NPFI Initial number of FP posts

Initial variables of other variables

NTRI(1) Initial number of discharged workers with FP

NTRI(2)	Initial number of discharged workers without FP
DFII	Initial number of the money to finance the self-employment
NCAI	Initial number of apparent necessary FP posts
ECAI	Initial number of apparent excess of posts of FP

Variable of control

ITML	Transparency index of the work market
DFAM	Monthly money to finance the self-employment

Variable of Scenario

CNCE	Capital necessary to create an enterprise
TNCE	Normal rate of enterprises increase
TRCP	Retard time of construction of FP posts
TREP	Retard time of excess of posts
NVAE (1)	Forecast of the number of vacancies of the environment directed to the people of "La Coma" with FP
NVAE (2)	Forecast of the number of Vacancies of the environment directed to the people of "La Coma" without FP.
TNDE	Normal rate of enterprises decrease
TDEC	Decrease rate by competition
NMTE (1)	Mean number of the (SE) by enterprise
NMTE (2)	Mean number of the (OE) by enterprise
IPAC (1)	Active population's increase with FP
IPAC (2)	Active population's increase without FP
NINL (1)	Immigrants workers with FP
NINL(2)	Immigrants workers without FP
PFFPA	Percentage of FP among the (OE)
DMCL	Mean duration of the contracts
PTAT	Percentage of temporal workers of the (OE)
PTBA(1)	Percentage of workers in that work in "La Coma" with FP
PTBA(2)	Percentage of workers in that work in "La Coma" without FP

Scenario 1 (tender)

In this scenario, we suppose that the actual uncontrollable variables will maintain its tendency in the next years.

Scenario 2 (pessimist):

In this scenario, we suppose that uncontrollable variables could tend to an unfavourable situation during the next years (capital increase

necessary to create the enterprise and work vacancies decrease).

Scenario 3 (optimist):

In this scenario, we suppose that uncontrollable variables could tend to a favourable situation during the next years (work vacancies increase).

Implementation of the Model

With the strategy 1, better results are obtained that with any other one. In the same way that in the optimistic scenario, smaller values than unemployment and bigger values of the index OBJM are reached.

As an immediate conclusion, it would be the one of implementing the strategy 1 in "La Coma". This would mean to make the entire possible to increase the transparency index of the work market and to increase the grants received by the employment creation.

The strategies that follow the first one in order of utility are: the 2nd, the 3rd and the 4th.

Conclusions

- The most important and developing contribution that the model makes is the scarcity existent difference between the results of the strategy 1 and those of the strategy 2. Therefore, significant differences exist between the strategies in which the index of transparency of the work market is maximised and those that do not maximise this variable, but the differences are not so evident inside each group. That is to say, although always the order of preference 1-2-3-4 is maintained, the strategies 1 and 2 are very nearest among themselves, as well as the 3rd with 4th. These results make see the importance of the transparency index of the work market (ITML).
- The ITML can not increase the value of OBJM as much as with DFAM, but in the optimistic scenario it is able to reduce more the total number of unemployed and to increase that of workers until better levels that in combination with DFAM (available monthly money to finance the self-employment).
- An important application can be extracted for the performances in "La Coma": it is more profitable to improve the communication among enterprises and unemployed that to create more enterprises

(FIGURE.1)

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